

Literature review on the diverse perspectives on fisheries at the global scale

Coded references

1. Agnew, D. J., Pearce, J., Pramod, G., Peatman, T., Watson, R., Beddington, J. R., & Pitcher, T. J. (2009). Estimating the worldwide extent of illegal fishing. *PLoS ONE*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0004570>
2. Al-Tarawneh, K. I. (2018). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Practice in Bahrain. *Journal of Business & Economic Policy*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.30845/jbep.v5n4a11>
3. Allison, E. H., Ratner, B. D., Åsgård, B., Willmann, R., Pomeroy, R., & Kurien, J. (2012). Rights-based fisheries governance: From fishing rights to human rights. *Fish and Fisheries*, 13(1), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2011.00405.x>
4. Almeida, O. T., Lorenzen, K., & McGrath, D. G. (2009). Fishing agreements in the lower Amazon: For gain and restraint. *Fisheries Management and Ecology*, 16(1), 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2400.2008.00647.x>
5. Arkema, K. K., Rogers, L. A., Toft, J., Mesher, A., Wyatt, K. H., Albury-Smith, S., Moultrie, S., Ruckelshaus, M. H., & Samhuri, J. (2019). Integrating fisheries management into sustainable development planning. *Ecology and Society*, 24(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10630-240201>
6. Baker-Médard, M. (2017). Gendering Marine Conservation: The Politics of Marine Protected Areas and Fisheries Access. *Society and Natural Resources*, 30(6), 723–737. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2016.1257078>
7. Barner, A. K., Lubchenco, J., Costello, C., Gaines, S. D., Leland, A., Jenks, B., Murawski, S., Schwaab, E., & Spring, M. (2015). Solutions for recovering and sustaining the bounty of the ocean. *Oceanography*, 28(2), 252–263. <https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2015.51>
8. Bavinck, M., Jentoft, S., & Scholtens, J. (2018). Fisheries as social struggle: A reinvigorated social science research agenda. *Marine Policy*, 94(December 2017), 46–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.04.026>
9. Belhabib, D., Lam, V. W. Y., & Cheung, W. W. L. (2016). Overview of West African fisheries under climate change: Impacts, vulnerabilities and adaptive responses of the artisanal and industrial sectors. *Marine Policy*, 71, 15–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.05.009>

10. Bell, J. D., Sharp, M. K., Havice, E., Batty, M., Charlton, K. E., Russell, J., Adams, W., Azmi, K., Romeo, A., Wabnitz, C. C. C., Andrew, N. L., Rodwell, L., Gu'urau, S., & Gillett, R. (2019). Realising the food security benefits of canned fish for Pacific Island countries. *Marine Policy*, *100*(October 2018), 183–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.10.034>
11. Bene, C. (2017). Marine reserves and food security: why we failed so far to build robust evidence. In *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper* (Vol. 603). <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i6742e.pdf>
12. Béné, C., & Friend, R. M. (2011). Poverty in small-scale fisheries: Old issue, new analysis. *Progress in Development Studies*, *11*(2), 119–144. <https://doi.org/10.1177/146499341001100203>
13. Bennett, E. (2005). Gender, fisheries and development. *Marine Policy*, *29*(5), 451–459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2004.07.003>
14. Bennett, N. J., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Blythe, J., Silver, J. J., Singh, G., Andrews, N., Calò, A., Christie, P., Di Franco, A., Finkbeiner, E. M., Gelcich, S., Guidetti, P., Harper, S., Hotte, N., Kittinger, J. N., Le Billon, P., Lister, J., López de la Lama, R., McKinley, E., ... Sumaila, U. R. (2019). Towards a sustainable and equitable blue economy. *Nature Sustainability*, *2*(11), 991–993. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0404-1>
15. Bennett, N. J., Kaplan-Hallam, M., Augustine, G., Ban, N., Belhabib, D., Brueckner-Irwin, I., Charles, A., Couture, J., Eger, S., Fanning, L., Foley, P., Goodfellow, A. M., Greba, L., Gregr, E., Hall, D., Harper, S., Maloney, B., Mclsaac, J., Ou, W., ... Bailey, M. (2018). Coastal and Indigenous community access to marine resources and the ocean: A policy imperative for Canada. *Marine Policy*, *87*(November 2017), 186–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.10.023>
16. Beseng, M. (2019). Cameroon's choppy waters: The anatomy of fisheries crime in the maritime fisheries sector. *Marine Policy*, *108*(May), 103669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103669>
17. Bogard, J. R., Thilsted, S. H., Marks, G. C., Wahab, M. A., Hossain, M. A. R., Jakobsen, J., & Stangoulis, J. (2015). Nutrient composition of important fish species in Bangladesh and potential contribution to recommended nutrient intakes. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, *42*, 120–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2015.03.002>
18. Cabral, R. B., Mayorga, J., Clemence, M., Lynham, J., Koeshendrajana, S., Muawanah, U., Nugroho, D., Anna, Z., Mira, Ghofar, A., Zulfainarni, N., Gaines, S. D., & Costello, C. (2018). Rapid and lasting gains from solving illegal fishing. *Nature Ecology and Evolution*, *2*(4), 650–658. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-018-0499-1>
19. Carvalho, N., Edwards-Jones, G., & Isidro, E. (2011). Defining scale in fisheries: Small versus large-scale fishing operations in the Azores. *Fisheries Research*, *109*(2–3), 360–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2011.03.006>

20. Cheung, W. W. L., Lam, V. W. Y., Sarmiento, J. L., Kearney, K., Watson, R., Zeller, D., & Pauly, D. (2010). Large-scale redistribution of maximum fisheries catch potential in the global ocean under climate change. *Global Change Biology*, *16*(1), 24–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01995.x>
21. Cheung, W. W., Lam, V. W., & Cc Wabnitz, C. (2019). *Fisheries; Climate change Future scenarios and projections for fisheries on the high seas under a changing climate Produced by IIED's Shaping Sustainable Markets Group Partner organisation* (Issue March). <http://pubs.iied.org/16653IIEDwww.iied.org@iiedwww.facebook.com/theIIED>
22. Cheung, W., Bruggeman, J., & Butenschon, M. (2018). *Chapter 4: Projected changes in global and national potential marine fisheries catch under climate change scenarios in the twenty-first century*.
23. Cinner, J. E. (2009). Poverty and the use of destructive fishing gear near east African marine protected areas. *Environmental Conservation*, *36*(4), 321–326. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892910000123>
24. Cinner, J. E., Basurto, X., Fidelman, P., Kuange, J., Lahari, R., & Mukminin, A. (2012). Institutional designs of customary fisheries management arrangements in Indonesia, Papua New Guinea, and Mexico. *Marine Policy*, *36*(1), 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.06.005>
25. Cinner, J. E., Daw, T. M., McClanahan, T. R., Muthiga, N., Abunge, C., Hamed, S., Mwaka, B., Rabearisoa, A., Wamukota, A., Fisher, E., & Jiddawi, N. (2012). Transitions toward co-management: The process of marine resource management devolution in three east African countries. *Global Environmental Change*, *22*(3), 651–658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.03.002>
26. Cinner, J. E., Daw, T., & McClanahan, T. R. (2009). Socioeconomic factors that affect artisanal fishers' readiness to exit a declining fishery. *Conservation Biology*, *23*(1), 124–130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2008.01041.x>
27. Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., & Sumaila, U. R. (2019). Busting myths that hinder an agreement to end harmful fisheries subsidies. *Marine Policy*, *109*(September). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103699>
28. Cohen, P. J., Allison, E. H., Andrew, N. L., Cinner, J., Evans, L. S., Fabinyi, M., Garces, L. R., Hall, S. J., Hicks, C. C., Hughes, T. P., Jentoft, S., Mills, D. J., Masu, R., Mbaru, E. K., & Ratner, B. D. (2019). Securing a just space for small-scale fisheries in the blue economy. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *6*(MAR), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00171>
29. Cole, S. M., McDougall, C., Kaminski, A. M., Kefi, A. S., Chilala, A., & Chisule, G. (2018). Postharvest fish losses and unequal gender relations: Drivers of the social-ecological trap in the Barotse Floodplain fishery, Zambia. *Ecology and Society*, *23*(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-09950-230218>
30. Costello, C., Ovando, D., Clavelle, T., Kent Strauss, C., Hilborn, R., Melnychuk, M. C., Branch, T. A., Gaines, S. D., Szuwalski, C. S., Cabral, R. B., Rader, D. N., & Leland, A. (2016). Global fishery prospects

under contrasting management regimes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 113(18), 5125–5129. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1520420113>

31. Crona, B. I., Van Holt, T., Petersson, M., Daw, T. M., & Buchary, E. (2015). Using social-ecological syndromes to understand impacts of international seafood trade on small-scale fisheries. *Global Environmental Change*, 35, 162–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.07.006>
32. Crona, B. I., Basurto, X., Squires, D., Gelcich, S., Daw, T. M., Khan, A., Havice, E., Chomo, V., Troell, M., Buchary, E. A., & Allison, E. H. (2016). Towards a typology of interactions between small-scale fisheries and global seafood trade. *Marine Policy*, 65, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.11.016>
33. Crona, B., & Bodin, Ö. (2010). Power Asymmetries in Small-Scale Fisheries. *Ecology and Society*, 15(4). <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26268218>
34. de Coning, E. (2011). *Transnational organized crime in the fishing industry: Focus on trafficking in persons; smuggling of migrants; illicit drugs trafficking*. 140. http://www.unodc.org/documents/human-trafficking/Issue_Paper_-_TOC_in_the_Fishing_Industry.pdf
35. De Greef, K., & Raemaekers, S. (2014). *South Africa's Illicit Abalone Trade: An Updated Overview And Knowledge Gap Analysis*. <http://www.traffic.org/storage/W-TRAPS-Abalone-report.pdf>
36. Doumbouya, A., Camara, O. T., Mamie, J., Intchama, J. F., Jarra, A., Ceesay, S., Guèye, A., Ndiaye, D., Beibou, E., Padilla, A., & Belhabib, D. (2017). Assessing the effectiveness of monitoring control and surveillance of illegal fishing: The case of West Africa. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4(MAR). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00050>
37. Fröcklin, S., De La Torre-Castro, M., Lindström, L., & Jiddawi, N. S. (2013). Fish traders as key actors in fisheries: Gender and adaptive management. *Ambio*, 42(8), 951–962. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-013-0451-1>
38. Fujita, R., Epstein, L., Battista, W., Karr, K., Higgins, P., Landman, J., & Carcamo, R. (2017). Scaling territorial use rights in fisheries (TURFs) in Belize. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 93(1), 137–153. <https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2016.1002>
39. Fujita, R., Tourgee, A., Carcamo, R., Epstein, L., Gedamke, T., McDonald, G., Wilson, J. R., & Foley, J. R. (2019). *Assessing and Managing Small-Scale Fisheries in Belize*. 177–195. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76078-0_8
40. Gagern, A., & van den Bergh, J. (2013). A critical review of fishing agreements with tropical developing countries. *Marine Policy*, 38, 375–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.06.016>

41. Gelcich, S., Cinner, J., Donlan, C. J., Tapia-Lewin, S., Godoy, N., & Castilla, J. C. (2017). Fishers' perceptions on the Chilean coastal TURF system after two decades: Problems, benefits, and emerging needs. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 93(1), 53–67. <https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2015.1082>
42. Gelcich, S., Hughes, T. P., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Defeo, O., Fernández, M., Foale, S., Gunderson, L. H., Rodríguez-Sickert, C., Scheffer, M., Steneck, R. S., & Castilla, J. C. (2010). Navigating transformations in governance of Chilean marine coastal resources. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107(39), 16794–16799. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1012021107>
43. Gelcich, S., Martínez-Harms, M. J., Tapia-Lewin, S., Vasquez-Lavin, F., & Ruano-Chamorro, C. (2019). Comanagement of small-scale fisheries and ecosystem services. *Conservation Letters*, 12(2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12637>
44. Gelcich, S., Reyes-Mendy, F., & Rios, M. A. (2019). Early assessments of marine governance transformations: Insights and recommendations for implementing new fisheries management regimes. *Ecology and Society*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10517-240112>
45. Golden, C. D., Allison, E. H., Cheung, W. W. L., Dey, M. M., Halpern, B. S., McCauley, D. J., Smith, M., Vaitla, B., Zeller, D., & Myers, S. S. (2016). Nutrition: Fall in fish catch threatens human health. *Nature*, 534(7607), 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1038/534317a>
46. Haines, S. (2020). Developing human rights at sea. *Ocean Yearbook*, 35(June).
47. Hanich, Q., Campbell, B., Bailey, M., & Molenaar, E. (2015). Research into fisheries equity and fairness—addressing conservation burden concerns in transboundary fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 51, 302–304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.09.011>
48. Harper, S., Grubb, C., Stiles, M., & Sumaila, U. R. (2017). Contributions by Women to Fisheries Economies: Insights from Five Maritime Countries. *Coastal Management*, 45(2), 91–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2017.1278143>
49. Harper, S., Zeller, D., Hauzer, M., Pauly, D., & Sumaila, U. R. (2013). Women and fisheries: Contribution to food security and local economies. *Marine Policy*, 39(1), 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.10.018>
50. Hauck, M., & Sweijd, N. A. (2017). A case study of abalone poaching in South Africa and its impact on fisheries management. *Green Criminology*, 223–231. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315093390-11>
51. ILO. (2016). Fishers first - Good practices to end labour exploitation at sea. *Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work Branch*.

52. Intchama, J. F., Belhabib, D., & Jumpe, R. J. T. (2018). Assessing Guinea Bissau's legal and illegal unreported and unregulated fisheries and the surveillance efforts to tackle them. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 5(APR), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00079>
53. International, I. C. C., & Bureau, M. (2016). *Piracy and Armed Rbbery against Ships: Report of the Period of 1 Jnauary -30 June 2016*. July, 1–26.
54. Interpol. (2018). *International Law Enforcement Cooperation in the Fisheries Sector*. February, 171.
55. Interpol Environmental Security Sub-Directorate. (2014). *Study on Fisheries Crime in the West*. September, 64.
56. Isaacs, M., & Witbooi, E. (2019). Fisheries crime, human rights and small-scale fisheries in South Africa: A case of bigger fish to fry. *Marine Policy*, 105(January), 158–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.12.023>
57. Jacquet, J. (2009). Silent water: A brief examination of the marine fisheries crisis. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 11(2), 255–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-007-9108-1>
58. Jentoft, S. (2007). Limits of governability: Institutional implications for fisheries and coastal governance. *Marine Policy*, 31(4), 360–370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2006.11.003>
59. Jentoft, S., Chuenpagdee, R., Franz, N., & Implementation, G. (2017). *The Small- Scale Fisheries Guidelines Global Implementation*. 850. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55074-9>
60. Johnston, S. J., & Butterworth, D. S. (2017). *Summary of South Coast rock lobster (Palinurus gilchristi) fishery*. 1–4.
61. Kaczynski, V. M., & Fluharty, D. L. (2002). European policies in West Africa: Who benefits from fisheries agreements? *Marine Policy*, 26(2), 75–93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-597X\(01\)00039-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-597X(01)00039-2)
62. Kaplan-Hallam, M., Bennett, N. J., & Satterfield, T. (2017). Catching sea cucumber fever in coastal communities: Conceptualizing the impacts of shocks versus trends on social-ecological systems. *Global Environmental Change*, 45(January), 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.05.003>
63. Kieffer, M. (n.d.). *Matthews et al 2012 gender perspective on livelihoods and fisheries*.
64. Kittinger, J. N., Teh, L. C. L., Allison, E. H., Bennett, N. J., Crowder, L. B., Finkbeiner, E. M., Hicks, C., Scarton, C. G., Nakamura, K., Ota, Y., Young, J., Alifano, A., Apel, A., Arbib, A., Bishop, L., Boyle, M., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Hunter, P., Le Cornu, E., ... Wilhelm, T. 'Aulani. (2017). Committing to socially responsible seafood: *Science*, 356(6341), 912–913. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aam9969>

65. Kruijssen, F., Audet-Belanger, G., Choudhury, A., Crissman, C. C., Dalsgaard, J. P. T., Dawson, C., Dickson, M., Genschick, S., Islam, M. M., Kaminski, A. M., Keus, H. J., McDougall, C. L., Banda, L., Muyaule, C., & Rajaratnam, S. (2016). *Value chain transformation: Taking stock of WorldFish research on value chains and markets*. 47. <https://www.worldfishcenter.org/content/value-chain-transformation-taking-stock-worldfish-research-value-chains-and-markets-0>
66. Kuzmianok, O. (n.d.). *Combating Transnational Organized Fisheries Crime : Global Challenges and International Cooperation*.
67. Kuzmianok, O. (n.d.). *Combating Transnational Organized Fisheries Crime : Global Challenges and International Cooperation*.
68. Lentisco, A., & Lee, R. (2015). A review of women's Access to Fish in Small-Scale Fisheries. In *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Circular No. 1098* (Vol. 1098, Issue August). <http://ezproxy.lib.ucalgary.ca/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eh&AN=109998014&site=ehost-live>
69. Levin, J. (2018). Seafood fraud and mislabelling across Canada. *Oceana*.
70. Matsue, N., Daw, T., & Garrett, L. (2014). Women Fish Traders on the Kenyan Coast: Livelihoods, Bargaining Power, and Participation in Management. *Coastal Management*, 42(6), 531–554. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2014.964819>
71. McCauley, D. J., Jablonicky, C., Allison, E. H., Golden, C. D., Joyce, F. H., Mayorga, J., & Kroodsma, D. (2018). Wealthy countries dominate industrial fishing. *Science Advances*, 4(8). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aau2161>
72. McClenachan, L., Neal, B. P., Al-Abdulrazzak, D., Witkin, T., Fisher, K., & Kittinger, J. N. (2014). Do community supported fisheries (CSFs) improve sustainability? *Fisheries Research*, 157, 62–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2014.03.016>
73. Neil, J. I. (2018). *The Maritime Commons : Digital Repository of the World Maritime IUU fishing : a gateway to transnational crimes in Jamaica IUU FISHING IN JAMAICA : A GATEWAY TO TRANSNATIONAL CRIMES*.
74. Nordic Council of Ministers. (2017). *Chasing Red Herrings - Flags of Convenience, Secrecy and the Impact on Fisheries Crime Law Enforcement*. March, 1–95.
75. Nurse, A. (2018). Green Crime in Mexico. In *Green Crime in Mexico*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75286-0>
76. OECD. (2013). *Evading the Net: Tax Crime in the Fisheries Sector*.

77. Okafor-Yarwood, I. (2019). Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, and the complexities of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) for countries in the Gulf of Guinea. *Marine Policy*, 99(May 2017), 414–422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.09.016>
78. Okafor-Yarwood, I. (2020). The Cyclical Nature of Maritime Security Threats: Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated Fishing as a Threat to Human and National Security in the Gulf of Guinea. *African Security*, 13(2), 116–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19392206.2020.1724432>
79. Österblom, H., & Folke, C. (2013). Emergence of global adaptive governance for stewardship of regional marine resources. *Ecology and Society*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05373-180204>
80. Osterblom, H., Jouffray, J. B., Folke, C., Crona, B., Troell, M., Merrie, A., & Rockström, J. (2015). Transnational corporations as “keystone actors” in marine ecosystems. *PLoS ONE*, 10(5), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0127533>
81. Pauly, D., Belhabib, D., Blomeyer, R., Cheung, W. W. W. L., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Copeland, D., Harper, S., Lam, V. W. Y., Mai, Y., Le Manach, F., Österblom, H., Mok, K. M., van der Meer, L., Sanz, A., Shon, S., Sumaila, U. R., Swartz, W., Watson, R., Zhai, Y., & Zeller, D. (2014). China’s distant-water fisheries in the 21st century. *Fish and Fisheries*, 15(3), 474–488. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12032>
82. Pauly, D., Watson, R., & Alder, J. (2005). Global trends in world fisheries: Impacts on marine ecosystems and food security. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 360(1453), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2004.1574>
83. Pauly, D., & Zeller, D. (2016). Catch reconstructions reveal that global marine fisheries catches are higher than reported and declining. *Nature Communications*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10244>
84. Plant, A. F. (1975). Oil on the waters. *Chemical and Engineering News*, 53(47), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cen-v053n047.p002>
85. Point, R. (2020). *Criminality and resilience. February.*
86. Pomeroy, R., Parks, J., Pollnac, R., Campson, T., Genio, E., Marlessy, C., Holle, E., Pido, M., Nissapa, A., Boromthanasarat, S., & Thu Hue, N. (2007). Fish wars: Conflict and collaboration in fisheries management in Southeast Asia. *Marine Policy*, 31(6), 645–656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2007.03.012>
87. Purcell, S. W., Crona, B. I., Lalavanua, W., & Eriksson, H. (2017). Distribution of economic returns in small-scale fisheries for international markets: A value-chain analysis. *Marine Policy*, 86(June), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.09.001>

88. Ramesh, N., Rising, J. A., & Oremus, K. L. (2019). Consequences of larval dispersal. *Science*, 1196(June 21), 1192–1196.
89. Researcher, S., & Africa, S. (2008). *U4BRIEF*. 5(1).
90. Rosales, R. M., Pomeroy, R., Calabio, I. J., Batong, M., Cedo, K., Escara, N., Facunla, V., Gulayan, A., Narvadez, M., Sarahadil, M., & Sobrevega, M. A. (2017). Value chain analysis and small-scale fisheries management. *Marine Policy*, 83(February), 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.05.023>
91. Sala, E., Mayorga, J., Costello, C., Kroodsmas, D., Palomares, M. L. D., Pauly, D., Sumaila, U. R., & Zeller, D. (2018). The economics of fishing the high seas. *Science Advances*, 4(6), eaat2504. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aat2504>
92. Santos, R., Pabon, A., Silva, W., Silva, H., & Pinho, M. (2020). Population structure and movement patterns of blackbelly rosefish in the NE Atlantic Ocean (Azores archipelago). In *Fisheries Oceanography* (Vol. 29, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/fog.12466>
93. Sarma, M., & Pais, J. (2008). Financial Inclusion and Development: A Cross Country Analysis. In *Annual Conference of the Human Development and Capability Association, New Delhi, 168(10–13)*, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid>
94. Schiller, L., Bailey, M., Jacquet, J., & Sala, E. (2018). High seas fisheries play a negligible role in addressing global food security. *Science Advances*, 4(8). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aat8351>
95. Schuhbauer, A., Chuenpagdee, R., Cheung, W. W. L., Greer, K., & Sumaila, U. R. (2017). How subsidies affect the economic viability of small-scale fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 82(March), 114–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.05.013>
96. Schutter, O. De. (2012). *a /67/268. 45640*(August).
97. Sonne, C., Jepson, P. D., Desforges, P., Alstrup, A. K. O., Olsen, M. T., Eulaers, I., Letcher, R. J., Melissa, A., & Dietz, R. (2018). Pollution threatens toothed whales migratory species Science outreach in the Borneo jungle. *Science*, 361, 8–10.
98. Spijkers, J., Singh, G., Blasiak, R., Morrison, T. H., Le Billon, P., & Österblom, H. (2019). Global patterns of fisheries conflict: Forty years of data. *Global Environmental Change*, 57(May). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.05.005>
99. Stacey, N., Gibson, E., Loneragan, N. R., Warren, C., Wiryawan, B., Adhuri, D., & Fitriana, R. (2019). Enhancing coastal livelihoods in Indonesia: an evaluation of recent initiatives on gender, women and sustainable livelihoods in small-scale fisheries. *Maritime Studies*, 18(3), 359–371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-019-00142-5>

100. Steinberg, J. (2014). The Illicit Abalone Trade in South Africa. *Deviant Globalization: Black Market Economy in the 21st Century*, April. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781501300936.ch-009>
101. Stringer, C., & Harré, T. (2019). Human trafficking as a fisheries crime? An application of the concept to the New Zealand context. *Marine Policy*, 105(February), 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.12.024>
102. Sumaila, U. R., Lam, V. W. Y., Miller, D. D., Teh, L., Watson, R. A., Zeller, D., Cheung, W. W. L., Côté, I. M., Rogers, A. D., Roberts, C., Sala, E., & Pauly, D. (2015). Winners and losers in a world where the high seas is closed to fishing. *Scientific Reports*, 5, 8481. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep08481>
103. Sumaila, U. R., Lam, V., Le Manach, F., Swartz, W., & Pauly, D. (2016). Global fisheries subsidies: An updated estimate. *Marine Policy*, 69, 189–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.12.026>
104. Sumaila, U. R., Jacquet, J., & Witter, A. (2017). When bad gets worse: Corruption and fisheries. *Corruption, Natural Resources and Development: From Resource Curse to Political Ecology*, 93–105. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785361203.00015>
105. Sundström, A. (2012). Corruption and regulatory compliance: Experimental findings from South African small-scale fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 36(6), 1255–1264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.03.013>
106. Talma, J., Kotze, J. ., Markovina, M., & Snijman, P. (2014). *A Multi-Agency Task Team Working together to end destructive blast fishing*. June, 1–3. http://www.fao.org/fi/oldsite/eims_search/1_dett.asp?calling=simple_s_result&lang=zh&pub_id=317379
107. Tickler, D., Meeuwig, J. J., Bryant, K., David, F., Forrest, J. A. H., Gordon, E., Larsen, J. J., Oh, B., Pauly, D., Sumaila, U. R., & Zeller, D. (2018). Modern slavery and the race to fish. *Nature Communications*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07118-9>
108. Tickler, D., Meeuwig, J. J., Palomares, M. L., Pauly, D., & Zeller, D. (2018). Far from home: Distance patterns of global fishing fleets. *Science Advances*, 4(8), 4–10. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aar3279>
109. US Department of State. (2012). *International Narcotics Control Strategy Report, Volume 1: Drug and Chemical Control*. I(March). <https://www.state.gov/documents/organization/253655.pdf>
110. USAID. (2016). *Fishing for Food Security: Importance of Wild Fisheries for Food Security and Nutrition*. April.
111. Vienne-Guerrin, N. (2020). Rotten. *Shakespeare's Insults*. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781780935898.eh348>

112. VITELLI, K. D. (2018). Document 1: In *Franchthi Neolithic Pottery, Volume 1* (pp. 223–248). <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv7xbrjm.41>
113. Walker, B. L. E. (2001). Sisterhood and Seine-Nets: Engendering Development and Conservation in Ghana's Marine Fishery. *Professional Geographer*, 53(2), 160–177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0033-0124.00277>
114. Wamukota, A. (2010). The Structure of Marine Fish marketing in Kenya: The Case of Malindi and Kilifi Districts. *Western Indian Ocean Journal of Marine Science*, 8(2), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.4314/wiojms.v8i2.56983>
115. Warcip. (2011). *Project Information Document (Pid) Concept Stage. 2003*, 48. http://www-wds.worldbank.org/external/default/WDSContentServer/WDSP/SDN/2012/03/02/DC1E490387859615852579B5004F558C/1_0/Rendered/PDF/P1230930PID0Print00302201201330698392242.pdf
116. Wildlife, C. (2020). *Mid-term independent project evaluation of the Fisheries Crime Initiative 'FishNET .'* March.
117. Williams, M. J., Porter, M., Choo, P. S., Kusakabe, K., Vuki, V., Gopal, N., & Bondad-Reantaso, M. (2012). Gender in aquaculture and fisheries: Moving the agenda forward. *Asian Fisheries Science*, 25(S), 1–13.
118. Williams, M. J. (2008). Why look at fisheries through a gender lens? *Development*, 51(2), 180–185. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dev.2008.2>
119. World Bank. (2012). Hidden harvest : The global contribution of capture fisheries. *The World Bank. Economic and Sector Work*, 66469, 92.
120. Yodanis, C. L. (2000). Constructing gender and occupational segregation: A study of women and work in fishing communities. *Qualitative Sociology*, 23(3), 267–290. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005515926536>
121. مقایسه اثر ترکیب های مختلف تمرین بدنی، مشاهده ای و تصویرسازی (1390). قلخانی منوچهر، حیرانی علی، ت. و. بر یادداری فوری و تاخیری مهارت سرویس بلند بدمینتون، رشد و یادگیری حرکتی-ورزشی.
122. King, C. (2014). Following the Proceeds of Environmental Crime: Fish, Forests and Filthy Lucre. In *Transnational Environmental Law*.
123. Brinson, A., Lee, M. Y., & Rountree, B. (2011). Direct marketing strategies: The rise of community supported fishery programs. *Marine Policy*, 35(4), 542–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.01.014>

124. D. Agnew. (2010). *West Africa Regional Fisheries Project ESTIMATION OF THE COST OF ILLEGAL FISHING IN WEST AFRICA FINAL REPORT*. May.
125. Moreto, W. D., Charlton, R. W., DeWitt, S. E., & Burton, C. M. (2020). The Convergence of CAPTURED Fish and People: Examining the Symbiotic Nature of Labor Trafficking and Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated Fishing. *Deviant Behavior*, 41(6), 733–749. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2019.1594587>
126. Sumaila, U. R., Zeller, D., Hood, L., Palomares, M. L. D., Li, Y., & Pauly, D. (2020). Illicit trade in marine fish catch and its effects on ecosystems and people worldwide. *Science Advances*, 6(9), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaz3801>
127. Devlin, C., Glaser, S. M., Villegas, C., & Poinsette, N. (n.d.). *Rough seas*.
128. Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO). (2015). Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-Scale Fisheries. In *Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-Scale Fisheries in the Context of Food Security and Poverty Eradication*. <http://www.fao.org/docrep/field/003/ab825f/AB825F00.htm#TOC>